

SECOND REPORT DISCOVERY PROJECTS

The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collection-Based Industrial Histories

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Science Museum Group | University of Leeds
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Executive Summary

Seventeen months into our three-year programme, *Congruence Engine* is broadly on time and on budget, addressing the stated aims and objectives; the project team is working selectively with the project partners (in the expectation that all will be enrolled across the duration of the project). Our systemic action research methodology is working well to organise the investigation, and tentative findings are emerging from it.

The ‘personality’ of *Congruence Engine* within the set of five Discovery Projects is clear: it is the project that is exploring and experimentally enacting what it would mean to potential future users of a national collection to be able to do historical and curatorial work in a world of cross-collection accessibility. We are selectively adopting the ‘social machine’ metaphor to articulate the combination of human intervention and programming affordances necessary to achieve this (Shadbolt et al 2022). The early project change away from using machine learning towards more ‘hand-stitched’ investigations was reversed in a decisive turn towards the digital in late 2022. Both of these changes of emphasis were linked to a deepening understanding of the ‘material conditions’ of the project, which has notably included the ease or difficulty of appointing people with key expertise, especially those with technical computing skills.

Staffing:

As in many large interdisciplinary projects employing part-time investigators with permanent contracts alongside numbers of (mainly early career) people on temporary contracts, *Congruence Engine* has, almost constantly, been negotiating shifting needs for time commitment and recruitment of new staff:

- The impossibility of recruiting a full-time three-year data scientist led in the first year to the pooling of the project’s wide range of digital expertise to support the investigation. After 11.5 months, it became possible to recruit Alex Butterworth as Project Lead, Digital History at the 60% he is available, enabling a concerted turn to digital methods. As a result, we have also recruited (or are in the process of recruiting) to at least four part-time and/or limited duration digital posts to support the investigations.
- The tragic early death of our Energy History Research Fellow Cameron Tailford in August has been hard for the team, but he has been very ably succeeded by Daniel Belteki.
- The resignation of our Project Manager after 5 months required a reorganisation, in which we, after an unsuccessful attempt to recruit, have very successfully combined our Action Research and Project Management functions, retaining Carol Chung, SMG Research Support Officer, at 40% to manage budget and contracts.
- The project’s Action Research is attentive to the constant need to retain the close involvement of all members of its team, especially in view of the very diverse disciplinary backgrounds of its members and the number of project partners.

Progress:

Our Systemic Action Research approach is paying dividends at both the macro- and the micro- scale: it enabled the project's successful digital turn, and supported the successful review of meetings infrastructure and digital management support programmes.

- The first round of investigations demonstrated the potential for linking together collections and data sources for historical enquiry, but all but one stitched-together small scale data, much as historians conventionally do. This successfully provoked the development of a means to work with bigger data, developing a methodology of using digital tools to construct pipelines between collections and linkable data. This depended on the recruitments noted under 'staffing'.
- The combined Action Research / Project Management approach operates via three regular meetings: a weekly project management meeting (attended by PI, Action Research Co-I and Fellow, Co-I for Digital History, Co-I for Digital Humanities, Project Manager and Coordinator); a fortnightly Investigations Meeting to guide the individual historical/digital investigations (same membership with the Digital Humanities Fellow (reporting data ingest and management) and representatives of each of the investigations in turn; and an alternating Fortnightly 'Digital Drop-In' for mutual technical and historical support (core membership: Kunika Kono, a member of the DH team, and any investigation-leaders requiring guidance).
- From late 2022, we added the Notion connected online workspace to our existing Basecamp subscription. Notion is the documentation core for the project, bringing together records of meetings and events, key documents, a team calendar, spaces for each of the investigations, and a section for regular diaries written by core team members. The writing, reading, and commenting aspects of using this tool (which is visible to the whole team, including project partners) enables close team communication, removing the need for lengthy updates in our online or in-person meetings.

The most outwardly visible output of the project from its first year is the [Special Issue](#) of the *Science Museum Group Journal*, published online and open access in early 2023, whose 18 articles articulate the aims, potential and progress of the project. The composition of its contributions, seen as a vector of the project's action research, was undertaken in parallel with the second cycle of research in the textiles strand.

Building on work in our first year, we are focussing our activities on three kinds of deliverables for differing audiences:

- For AHRC, in early 2024, we are providing a set of general recommendations from our research, framing worked examples from our investigations of the combination of human involvement and digital technique required to create instances of the national collection. We express this within the conceptual foundation of 'to national collection as verb', which is to say that our finding is that it is mistaken to assume that the national collection is a noun, an already existing entity that requires only to be joined-up. The potential national collection when viewed in terms of the contents of its parts, is, effectively, infinitely deep and detailed and only digitised, if at all, to a very superficial degree. And so, the working national collection must be created as needed as the outcome of linkages created by people undertaking historical and curatorial research. We describe the socio-

technical practice of creation as a ‘social machine’, and are framing our contribution as a ‘design specification’ for that social machine.

- For general museum-visiting audiences, we are producing a digital exhibit that aims briefly to convey: the purposes of TaNC, the scope of Congruence Engine, and the results of selected investigations. We are now planning on a minimum of two instantiations of the exhibit: in Newcastle in autumn 2023, and Bradford in Autumn 2024. Amongst its assets will be project films that we will also make available online.
- For the different communities and disciplines represented in the whole project team and its partners, we aim to develop both engagement and publications: In year three, we plan to run a programme of workshops and paid secondment opportunities for knowledge transfer and learning, especially for people in the heritage sector, to learn the techniques the research has trialled. Furthermore, we will produce a set of worked interpretive publications by December 2024 that demonstrate and advocate for these kinds of approaches. In this way, we plan to make the case for the national collection to historians and curators, both amateur and professional. Initial discussions point to perhaps one book of essays and one edited journal collection, alongside individual papers in a wide range of journals. We have moved our end of project conference to October 2024 to coincide with the meeting of the Artefacts international consortium for research in science museums, which traditionally meets at this time of year.

Research Results:

Our results derive from what we have learned about the implications of the project proposal to conduct a diversity of investigations at the interface of digital-technological possibility and historical / curatorial need. It is a significant conceptual development to be clear that the national collection is a potential to be realised through digital-historical practice, rather than a pre-existing totality awaiting a search engine. That is what we mean when we allude to the verbing of ‘national collection’. The means to achieve this national collection, we argue, is through very many acts of digital translation and linkage between collections entities. For this we need the power of digital technique and the intervention of human understanding and activity, for which conjunction we find Tim Berners-Lee’s ‘social machine’ metaphor a valuable description. At this time of rapid flux in the technologies, it remains valuable to address underlying needs and principles. Our approach sees the creation of a national collection as the product of a vast multiplicity of contributory acts, for which – we argue – it will be necessary to use a federated, rather than top-down, approach to governance.

These broad findings will contribute to the three categories of deliverable listed above. With respect to our interim recommendations, we propose:

- that the creation of the national collection should be undertaken through linkage of existing and specially created ‘connective tissue’ data, rather than by systematised aggregation of identically formatted data.
- Creation and use of a national collection must take account of participants’ motivations, enabling them to become involved in ways that feel useful to them.
- A national collection should offer multiple flexible pipeline processes to enable people to contribute, analyse and connect collections depending on their specific requirements.

- *Congruence Engine* recommends development of a suite (or registry) of tools and services that can be maintained and updated, allowing researchers and national collection users to choose those most appropriate for them, depending on their needs and the datasets in question.
- We recommend that no attempt is made to create a new overarching data standard, but instead, a series of standard data mappings that allow collections of different types (archive, museums, libraries, Wikidata, personal collections or community archives) to be linked.
- *Congruence Engine* recommends that consideration of necessary digitisation go beyond digital images or flat digital files to digitisation processes that make analogue material machine-readable. TaNC should adopt a broad definition of ‘the national collection’ to incorporate datasets including, for example, the census, or data from within archives rendered machine-readable, because these data enable the linkage of conventional GLAM collection items.
- Technology alone cannot create a sustainable and generative national collection. Alongside any resource for technical infrastructure, the national collection requires resource for staff, training and long-term skills development. There are important questions to be addressed relating to the siloeing of different kinds of expertise – digital, historical and curatorial – often reinforced by distinct language and working cultures. We recommend investment in career paths for individuals to gain hybrid skills to enable the linked national collection within the coming age of more digital curatorship and scholarship.
- A national collection as social machine will need a distributed and federated governance structure, one that enables local decision-making and contribution and does not require central control.
- Industrial heritage is a record of British colonial expansion and capitalist extraction. To see the national collection as a social machine offers a means of understanding how better to approach this subject, by activating different collections, knowledge and positions.

Abstract

The capacity to make strong connections between historical objects and sources lies at the heart of this project as it does in the everyday museum and historical practices that it is designed to support. Curators creating displays combine artefacts, images, audio-visual materials and histories often drawn from several heritage organisations. Family and local historians connect records from a diversity of sources that illuminate ancestors and localities so as to establish their genealogy or to understand the past of where they live. Academic historians patiently and critically connect a diverse range of archive sources with existing literature to tell new stories about the past. All rely on connecting different fragments of the past as they sew the quilts of narrative that constitute our local and national histories. The difference with this *Towards a National Collection* project is that it seeks to make such linkages at the national scale of all collections, enabling access together to significant numbers of relevant items from across many GLAM organisations holding heritage in many media. In place of the two-dimensional ranked list of search engines, we aim, with *Congruence Engine*, to model a world in which users will be able to explore data neighbourhoods where a great diversity of information about heritage items from many sources that are deeply relevant to their investigations will be readily to hand – museum objects, archive documents, pictures, films, buildings, and the records of previous investigations and relevant activity.

Congruence Engine may be characterised as a kind of ‘social machine’ (Shadbolt *et al* 2022), a form of socio-technical practice that requires both human propulsion and intervention in conjunction with the affordances of computing (including machine learning) techniques. The project is modelling the hybrid technical-historical practices that will be necessary whenever any kind of user wishes to undertake cross-collections work for curatorial and/or historical purposes. Our outputs address three kinds of audience: for the TaNC Directorate, we will provide a ‘design specification’ of our ‘social machine’ replete with worked examples and overarching meta-considerations. For the Museum-visiting public, we are creating a digital exhibit that shows how a national collection for industrial history might be created. For the workers in our home disciplines, we will run engagement events and publish worked pieces of scholarship that also advocate for the virtues of working digitally across collections.

Aims and Objectives

As we describe in more detail elsewhere (8.1), our project review towards the end of 2022 allowed us to enact two crucial changes to the project: a decisive turn to ensure a digital core to all our investigations, and the combining of our Project Management and Action Research Work Packages. In this, the latter has enabled the delivery of the former, via a redesigned set of regular meetings. Below we quote the original application's aims and objectives (selectively modified in light of project experience), adding a commentary on the research so far, and what it has taught us.

1. Via an action research methodology to use real-world historical enquiries of community-, museum- and university-based historians and curators to hone digital tools needed for proof of concept of a linked national collection, using the example of industrial history.

The action research methodology has been a core resource for the conduct of the project from the outset, setting the tone of the enquiry from the opening conference in February 2022 onwards. In the funding application, we explained how the action research approach enables project members to respond to the emergence of unforeseen research opportunities. As we anticipated, it has been valuable at the micro- and the macro- scale, enabling the project to flex the investigation in response to pressures or, indeed, opportunities emergent from the research. In particular, it enabled our 'digital turn' in late 2022.

Reflection on the textiles workshops helped clarify that, even while we seek wider involvement, in this project valid participation comes just as much from other professionals within the heritage sector as it does from community groups. This initial phase of activating ourselves as a social machine was necessary to understand what this might mean for wider involvement. The next phase will focus on a wider ecology of our social machine. All of our participatory work is therefore more about specifying the means by which different people and groups can define the terms of their involvement (and the overall governance implications of a federated system) than about any tokenistic inclusion or involvement practice.

2. To conduct three industrial sector-based investigations using heterogeneous collections.
 - Textiles, energy and communications are here used to map the changing history of industry, society and culture over 250 years.

The project has taught us that the sketched sequential approach giving nine months' attention to each of the three industrial sectors is not practicable. This is partially because it took a cycle of action research to demonstrate that it would be necessary to find a way, despite recruitment difficulties, to make the project more digital, employing more digital tools and using large datasets. We are working pragmatically to develop the investigations even while we await the full availability of our more technical appointees. It also became clear that – at least at this experimental stage – the cycles of research activity would mostly tend to be longer than the three months initially envisaged. The result is that we are now conducting research across the three themes in a layered

manner, with the textiles research establishing possibilities and principles that are providing the context for the energy, then communications, investigations to develop in parallel.

3. To represent museum culture and STEM history within the set of Discovery Projects.

The differences between museum styles of research ('museum as method'; Thomas 2010, Boon 2022) and those of the Academy have risen up the project's agenda, because kinds of practice that draw on many collections and on differing media are typical of museum work (especially in display), but less so in the universities. Histories of science, technology, engineering and medicine represented in our consortium also occur in at least one other Discovery Project, but in Congruence Engine they are the core concern. Furthermore, the collections we can link are products of the collecting histories of institutions; in the case of technical museums, understanding how our curatorial ancestors conceptualised the history of technology is key to unlocking understanding of the collections that exist, and the relative ease of linking them to undertake work in social history, for example.

4. To pursue kinds of interdisciplinary and intermedial research that are specifically enabled by the uniting of heterogeneous kinds of heritage items and their data.

The research is necessarily interdisciplinary, even at the level of combining humanities with digital expertise; the action research adds a third kind of practice to the mix, whilst recognising that museum modes of research (see 3) differ from those of universities adds a fourth. We are committed to making the research inter- not just multi-disciplinary.

The project consortium was planned with the aim of enabling intermedial studies; these are expected to bear fruit especially in the second half of the current investigations, once linkable terms have been extracted from different kinds of collection.

5. To conduct the investigation UK-wide: Bradford, Manchester, Newcastle, London, Edinburgh, etc.

In addition to the sites of planned activity, we have Project Partners from across the UK, including National Museums Northern Ireland and Amgueddfa Cymru.

6. To create appropriate outputs for all audiences: general and enthusiast public and scholars.

Interested individuals can already read the project blog (twelve issues written as of 6 February 2023). The special issue of the Science Museum Group Journal is now available open access to anyone. In conjunction with our major project reorientation, we made the decision to delay the digital exhibit's first iteration (of at least two) to autumn 2023, when it will premiere at partner institution, the Discovery Museum, Newcastle.

7. To create, enable and sustain a multidisciplinary team with appropriate skills to deliver the project aims.

The Action Research methodology is working well to convene the team. Still working hybrid (which is necessary for such a distributed team) we are moving to maximise the opportunities for working

together in person, for example by adding a second core team day (Monday) to the existing day (Wednesday) for those members of the team readily able to travel to London, and by opportunistically holding meetings around project events. We have a three-tier training programme in digital skills (see Sustainability and Infrastructure).

8. To enhance the cross-disciplinary skills of participants, especially the employability of early career researchers (ECRs).

The ECRs (and indeed the whole team) are working across disciplines, learning digital, curatorial, historical and participative skills. All team members are able to draw on each other's wide and deep experience.

9. To test the application of a range of digital techniques and technologies, including a range of Machine Learning/AI methods, in identifying and modelling potential linkage between heterogeneous datasets, of varying analogue/digital/machine-readable/semantically-modelled status. To reflect critically on consequent issues including biases in existing collections, processes of digitisation, the digitalisation of existing method, and the emergence of new AI techniques, and ethical considerations in relation to these.

In the first phase of the project, a wide variety of readily accessible digital tools was used and critiqued, including as components in pipelines for achieving particular purposes and outputs. Upstream, a variety of methods for image parsing and segmentation was tested as a first step towards data extraction, for example from large collection of historic Trade Directories. Separately, work with the University of Leicester has involved the preparation of textual corpora derived from audio sources, using machine learning approaches. Similar methods are expected to be used and tested in the collaboration with the Sussex Text Analysis Group Lab to create candidate alignment between content of collections metadata fields, for purposes of linkage/integration. Initial work towards defining an occupations ontology and a series of associated entity-specific (place, activity, object, material, etc) data resources has formed a distinct area of proof-of-concept activity over the last nine months. Our 'Lost Mills' investigation involves a practical investigation of how to integrate controlled vocabularies and thesauri, and polygonised data requests, as required by Historic England's suite of diverse databases.

All these technical means are detailed in the Research Approach section below.

10. To nurture dialogue in the digital humanities space between heritage/ humanities and data/computation.

See 4 above. In recognising the under-explored research potential of cultural heritage and collections data, the wider TaNC agenda implicitly requires that critical questions be addressed concerning where material culture is situated within the research culture of the humanities broadly and Digital Humanities specifically. These are inevitably encountered in the course of work on Congruence Engine, and may be productively examined in the context of envisioning systemic change that is enabled by the Action Research methodology. They include the distinct cultures of academic and curatorial practice and how both the potential of novel digital methods and the mediation effected by a social machine (designed for purposes of 'national collection' by diverse communities of interest) may erode or bridge these. Broader questions

too are raised and are being considered around resistance to unfamiliar methods and frameworks of operation, and legitimate concerns for ownership in developing data, the maintenance of professional status, and traditions of validation in knowledge production.

11. To work with other Discovery projects and AHRC to maximise the benefits and legacy of TaNC.

We look forward to greater collaborations as the projects mature. See Cross-Project Collaboration section below.

Partnership Structure

Funded Partners

- Science Museum Group, base for Principal Investigator (PI) Tim Boon and Co-Investigators (Co-Is): Alex Butterworth, John Stack, Jamie Unwin and Dave Patten; Research Fellows: Daniel Belteki, Stefania Zardini-Lacedelli, Daniel Wilson, Sarah Middle, Felix Needham-Simpson and Duncan Hay
- University College London, base for Co-I Jon Agar (Communications history)
- University of Leeds, base for Co-I: Helen Graham and Research Fellow Arran Rees (Action Research), and Co-Is Simon Popple (Digital Community engagement) and Graeme Gooday (Energy History),
- Liverpool University, base for Co-I William Ashworth (Textiles history)
- School of Advanced Study, University of London, base for Co-I Jane Winters and Research Fellow Anna-Maria Sichani (Digital Humanities)
- Historic England, base for Co-I Matt Bristow (Historic Environment)
- British Film Institute, base for Co-I Patrick Russell (Film)
- National Museums Scotland, base for Co-I Geoff Belknap (Communications history)
- Bradford Industrial Museum, Collaborating Organisation, base for Lizzie Llabres (Textiles history)
- Discovery Museum, Collaborating Organisation, base for Kylea Little (Energy history)
- Madlab, base for Asa Calow (Digital technique and participation)
- Wikimedia UK, base for Stuart Prior and Daria Cybulska (interactions and collaborations over Wikidata)

We also expect to sign contracts with:

- University of Sussex (involvement in NERF and data field alignment investigations)

Unfunded Project Partners (data providers and collaborators), with known areas of active participation

- BBC History and Heritage / Programme Index (likely involvement in exhibit)
- Birmingham Museums Trust (involvement in Journal)
- BT Archives (involvement in Communications investigation)
- Grace's Guide to Industrial History (involvement in energy investigation)
- History of Science Society: Isis Bibliography (involvement in literature investigation)
- The National Archives (involvement in textiles investigation)
- National Museum Wales (involvement in energy investigation)
- National Museums of Northern Ireland (involvement in textiles investigation)
- The National Trust (involvement in textiles investigation)
- Saltaire World Heritage Education Association (involvement in textiles investigation)
- Society for the History of Technology Bibliography (involvement in literature investigation)
- Tools of Knowledge Project (involvement in several investigations)
- Victoria and Albert Museum (involvement in textiles investigation)

We also expect to sign contracts with:

- University of Leicester (involvement in trade directories and oral history investigations)
- National Coal Mining Museum (involvement in energy investigation)

Staffing Structure

Each of the eight work packages is the responsibility of one lead investigator (some with other investigators), and most have an associated research fellow.

We have been able to resolve our earlier staffing challenges: by combining the Project Management function with the Action Research, we have achieved an agile and effective way of managing the project, whose success is no longer endangered by the difficulty in recruiting project managers that has been experienced across TaNC. (We retain the services of Carol Chung, the SMG Research Support Officer, at 40% FTE as Project Manager for budget and contract oversight.) The project's capacity to address its objectives in a data-intensive and digital-focussed manner has been transformed by the appointment of Alex Butterworth as Project Lead, Digital History; his understanding of what is required has enabled us to make several more appointments on the digital side: Felix Needham-Simpson (Research Assistant: Data Wrangling and Development) and Sarah Middle, Duncan Hay and Jennie Williams (part time / short duration Research Fellows in Digital Humanities). The School of Advanced Study has also contributed the services of digital specialists, Kunika Kono and Kaspar Beelen. We are fortunate after the tragic early death of Research Fellow Cameron Tailford to have been able to recruit Daniel Belteki in his place.

Below are the top line research question for each (some edited reflecting development within the project):

Umbrella WP1:

Tim Boon, PI

- How may we use computational techniques to enable linkage between UK industrial history collections of all kinds and scales for historical and curatorial purposes?

Digital History WP2:

Alex Butterworth with John Stack (SMG oversight)

- How can we apply machine learning and other computational techniques to support real-world historical enquiry? How does digital mediation - and the digitalisation of methods - change historical practice, including the narratives historians and others may construct? What considerations should inform the design of interfaces, of all kinds (visualisation, haptic, etc), to historical data?

Digital Humanities WP3:

Jane Winters; Research Fellow, Anna-Maria Sichani

- How do technology choices affect research processes and introduce biases, with what ethical implications? What skills are needed to equip the creators of the National Collection, and how can these be acquired? What infrastructures are required, including for data management?

Participatory Action Research WP4:

Helen Graham; Research Fellow, Arran Rees

- How can systemic action research technique be used to understand the challenges of realising a national collection of industrial history?

Digital exhibit WP5:

Dave Patten with Alex Butterworth

- How can we best use digital exhibits in museum contexts to present data and narratives in a way that enables visitors to engage with, and the project to gain insights into public interest in, the project's objectives?

Historical / curatorial WPs 6-8:

- How does attention to assemblages of data on heterogeneous heritage items – objects, pictures, archives, films, TV and radio programmes, recordings, buildings, maps, places, etc – treated as historical sources – affect the historical narratives that historians, communities and curators may construct?
 - Textiles: Will Ashworth; Research Fellow, Stefania Zardini-Lacedelli; associated museum: Bradford Industrial Museum (Lizzie Llabres, Lauren Padgett)
 - Energy: Graeme Gooday; Research Fellow, Daniel Belteki; associated museum: Discovery Museum Newcastle (Kylea Little, Bernard Musesengwe)
 - Communications: Jon Agar; Research Fellow, Daniel Wilson; associated museum: National Museums Scotland (Geoff Belknap).

Whilst we started the project using a working group model, supported by the BaseCamp project management tool, that allowed people to set up organising structures as they needed, we have since moved beyond the active facilitation of these. We dedicated time, at the beginning, to making space for divergence, as well as congruence. We did this to enable parallel and distributed action, led by those motivated by the topic of the working groups, in a loosely bounded, but centrally charted, environment that would really help unleash people's potential to innovate – both practically and conceptually. We were always clear that this approach was not static and would probably need to change as the project developed. Around nine months in, after observing and reflecting on how the working groups were developing, we noted that they were not as dynamic as we had hoped they might be, and that meetings and actions were happening more informally than at a working group level. So, whilst we knew parallel work was happening, to really start cohering a sense of collective understanding of that work, we decided to use more active facilitation methods. Our new meetings ecology – discussed in more detail in the research approach section – aims to cohere all the investigations. In doing this, we are seeking to invite the multiple parallel investigations into conversation with a group of people who, in turn, notice crossovers, emergent challenges and opportunities, and try to develop a sense of collective understanding about the findings of project. (We retain BaseCamp for broad whole project communications, but are finding Notion more valuable for documentation.)

Figure 1: Notion landing page

Overall Programme

Figure 2: Overall programme

Events and Consultations

	Item		Name	Number reached		URL
20-Oct-21	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories	Post-award Presentation	Tim Boon	50	SMG Collections Team	
28-Jan-22	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories: SMG All Staff Briefing	Event	Tim Boon	300	SMG All Staff	
Dec-2021	Project Webpage Created	Website			General	https://tinyurl.com/CongEng
Jan-2022	Project Blog Created	Website			General	https://ceblog.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk/
9-11-Feb-22	Congruence Engine Opening Conference	Event		50	Co-Is, Project Partners, Project Board, Steering Committee	
Mar-22	Project Basecamp	Website		50	Co-Is, Project Partners, Project Board, Steering Committee	https://3.basecamp.com/5316423/projects
20-21-Jun-22	Textiles Planning Workshop (Leeds)	Workshop		15	Co-Is and Project Partners for Textiles, CE SMG Team	The textiles pilot workshop, 20/21 June, Leeds
22-Jul-22	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories: Session at Annual Conference of the British Society for the History of Science, Belfast	Event	Tim Boon, Jon Agar, Graeme Gooday	40	BSSH delegates: historians of science and technology	

27-Jul-22	Textiles Reflection and Planning Workshop (London)	Workshop		15	Co-Is and Project Partners for Textiles, CE SMG Team	
19-Aug-22	Panel discussion contribution on CE to 'Industrial Labour and Cultural Engagement in the Long 19th Century' conference of the 'Piston, Press and Pen' AHRC project	Conference	Tim Boon	30	Historians of 19thc literature and history	https://tinyurl.com/CEIndLabour
20-21 Oct 22	Textiles Planning Workshop (Manchester)	Workshop		22	Co-Is, Project Partners and Participants for Textiles, CE SMG Team	
17-18 Nov 22	Science Museum Group Research Conference 2022	Workshop, Panel	Tim Boon, Stefania Zardini-Lacedelli, Will Ashworth	150	SMG staff, Postgraduate students of Science and Technology, CE Co-Is and project partners for Textiles	
17-20 Nov 22	The Congruence Engine: New Techniques to Link Collections for HSTM: HSS Annual Meeting 2022, Chicago	Event	Rebekah Higgitt (for Tim Boon)	30	HSS Members, Academic Historians of Science	
Nov 22	Project Notion site initiated	Website			General	https://tinyurl.com/CongEngWiki
19-Jan-23	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories, NRM Science Museum Group Staff Briefing	Presentation	Tim Boon	100	SMG NRM Staff	

6-7 Mar - 23	UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Community Congress (Birmingham)	Event	Anna Maria Sichani	150	Academics, Researchers, Digital professionals	
23- Mar-23	Reframing Failure: It's Complicated - Collaborations and Partnerships (online)	Panel	Arran Rees and Helen Graham		SAS delegates, Digital Humanities academics and professionals	
27-28 Mar 23	Social Machine Workshop (Newcastle)	Workshop	CE investigators and researchers	23	Co-Is, Project Partners and Participants (Discovery Museum), CE SMG Team	

Research Approach

We are running Congruence Engine using a systemic action research approach, one that is designed to enable the investigation of complexity and whole system change. The central philosophy of participatory approaches to action research is to research ‘with’ rather than ‘on’ people in ways that value practical as well as theoretical knowledge – ‘the creative action of people to address issues that matter to them’ (Heron and Reason 2001). Like many participatory projects delivered under the AHRC-led ‘Connected Communities’ theme, Congruence Engine includes multiple participants. It is taking a distinctively systemic action research methodology that makes this possible.¹ Here we are influenced by Danny Burns’ elaborations of systemic approaches to action research (2007; 2014), which offer practical ways to design participatory research at scale in ways which enable different parallel inquiries and crosscutting events to draw together the insights they produce. Design principles common to many strands of action research are: Multiple perspectives – we cannot understand the complexity of barriers to accessing and using collections only from the academic perspective; we must allow for a plurality of motivations and experiences (Burns 2007); Value different ways of knowing – all are intrinsically valuable; in our endeavour we need the experiential and affective as much as specific empirical knowledge (Heron & Reason 2001; Burns 2007); Learn together through doing – we cannot understand challenges to establishing a national collection only in a theoretical way; we need to try, test and push the systems that already exist to work out how they can change (Bradbury et al 2019). To these principles systemic action research adds: An improvisatory approach to change – real benefits come from being responsive to, and working with, what arises through the enquiry process (rather than sticking to a fixed plan); Going where the energy is – people being able to work on what has urgency and meaning for them is powerful; Divergence and Convergence – in a large interdisciplinary team we need to make space for people to be able to pursue their specific technical or historical interests and also bring the insights generated together to create shared meaning. The action research methodology, as well as enabling the research, collectively convenes all of us as participants to collaboratively trace, document and develop the project, evaluating barriers encountered. It constantly interrogates and refines the formulation and value of the project aim.

Progress

Publication in early 2023 of the *Congruence Engine* special issue of the *Science Museum Group Journal* was a major project milestone, with its 18 contributions by 28 authors. The writing of the journal was conceived as a part of the action research, rather than simply an output. In writing it, different constellations of project researchers interacted and collaborated to make sense of the work that the project’s first year had done. The authors experiment with different ways of knowing and knowledge

¹ CI Graham has successfully run two substantial AHRC projects, *Heritage Decisions* (with Boon as CI, AH/K006754/1) and *Bradford’s National Museum* (with SMG Science and Media Museum, AH/P008585/1) using this approach.

production, producing traditional single-authored pieces charting the different connections being made, collaborative dialogic pieces, and visually-led photographic and film essays.

Having run our first large action research cycle between March and November 2022, the project took the period from November into January 2023 to reflect, re-organise and re-orientate itself based on the learning from the first year. The core need we were responding to here arose from the experience of the first cycle of investigations: that the vast majority of these used small data and were therefore ‘hand-stitched’ in their character; that is, whilst they certainly linked collections items and historical practice, they were closer to standard historical practice than to the specifically digital methods and the larger scale that we need to investigate.

Informed by our reflections on the first phase of the project, we have cohered the project around the idea of the national collection as a ‘social machine’. Enabled by the action research approach, *Congruence Engine* models the kinds of activity involved in developing a national collection, working via multiple investigations with the aim of drawing together a design specification from the social and technical requirements we are identifying along the way.

To support that, we have combined the action research and project management aspects of the project and developed a new meetings ecology to support the multiple pipeline enquiries currently ongoing. At fortnightly Investigations Meetings, those responsible for the individual enquiries bring their proposals and research in progress to be guided; the meetings also oversee the overall balance. These meetings are complemented by digital drop-in sessions that allow researchers leading investigations to talk through and learn more about potential digital tools and approaches to their work, and provide more humanities-grounded context to their investigations for the digital-focused researchers collaborating with them. This also serves to identify further training needs that can be addressed on a quick-turnaround basis.

The multiple investigations now under way (see 2, below) are in dialogue with our provisional lead metaphor of ‘the national collection as a social machine’. Each individual investigation runs through cycles of planning, action, observation, reflection, and coming back to the Investigation Meetings for advice and steering. These cycles of activity and interaction into which the Investigations Meetings and Digital Drop-Ins are constantly feeding, develop understanding of the interactions between people and digital programs – the ‘social machine’ – iteratively helping us to specify its technical and social requirements.

1. The following account of the progress on the project’s current core activities is split into three sections: Reflections from the first full action research cycle, and the project’s digital re-emphasis
2. Running multiple investigations in parallel
3. Decolonising industrial heritage and designing an anti-oppressive national collection as social machine

The project’s digital re-emphasis; reflections from the first full action research cycle

What started as the ‘textiles pilot’ developed into the textiles strand of the project, across four workshops, developing investigation ideas in dialogue with community and sector partners. Whilst several of the current investigations were seeded at these workshops, we found that, as we have said, the investigations were focusing on what we referred to as the ‘hand-stitched’ level of work; small scale examples of how connections between discrete subsets of data might help bring about new insights for

historians, amateur and professional. Working through the pipelines of this kind of work is, of course, important for understanding the different ways people will approach interacting with a national collection, and reveals areas where particular kinds of technological support or intervention are productive. But the project team was also aware of the need to work with larger datasets, heterogeneous data, and to use novel machine learning techniques more actively.

In November 2022 we were able to increase Alex Butterworth's time on the project (to 0.6 FTE) and he became Co-I, Project Lead, Digital History. Through a period of reflection and planning forward, the project sharpened its digital through-line and surfaced the pipeline processes that the investigations would experiment with. The core process under investigation concerns how to create machine-readable linkable heritage data from catalogue records and archive materials. There are different tools, methods and techniques to move material down the pipeline, depending on its initial state (e.g. an analogue printed catalogue or a collection of digital oral histories). This sharpened approach, supported by the fortnightly Investigation Meetings, and alternate fortnightly Digital Drop-In sessions, constituted a digital re-balancing of the project. Alongside the reflective and re-organising work, and in acknowledgement of the difficulties in recruiting specific digital expertise, the project has arranged a more responsive hiring model within the Science Museum Group. This has resulted in the recruitment of the flexible digital-focused roles, and contracts with organisations, to contribute to and enhance the digital innovation work of the investigations (see 5, Staffing Structure).

Running multiple investigations in parallel

The project is currently working with nine individual investigations, running in parallel, and led by different researchers. We learned in year one that working digitally at scale requires longer timescales than our initial planning could manage (not least because of the need to appoint new digitally capable staff, and to let small contracts, before some kinds of work could be undertaken). Accordingly, we have moved from serial attention - first to textiles, second to energy and third to communications - to a practice in which thematic investigations are overlapping, whilst transferability of techniques across themes is constantly being addressed. Hence, textiles work continues in dialogue with the energy strand, and with the communications strand, which is preparing to get under way.

As we explain above, the investigations are seeking to explore historical and professional practice questions whilst experimenting with different pipelines that take collections of heritage material or datasets and transform them into linkable, machine-readable data. We expect in early 2024 to provide to the TaNC Directorate a 'specification' of the practice and 'operation' of the 'social machine', along with broad observations on barriers to, and affordances in, the creation of a national collection by these means. For the remainder of 2024, we will be completing investigations and reporting them via publication, workshops and secondments (for practitioners and academics) and exhibits (museum visitors) to demonstrate the possibilities of new kinds of curatorial and historical work employing data linkage between collections.

The current investigations include:

1&2. Oral Histories as connective sources; Connecting workers' songs with mining and textile connections: a cross-strand investigation. Investigating speech-to-text and natural language processing for 1. oral histories and 2. folk songs as a way of creating machine readable data, disambiguating entities and sentiments within the audio recordings, and creating connections between items in other collections through those extracted entities.

3. **Deeper catalogue data:** Making the most of rich collections information in historical museum catalogues that, for a variety of technical and social reasons, have not made their way into digitised catalogue systems. The investigation experiments with several methods (Ngrams, surprising phrase detection) to extract object names as training data for NER tools so that we may more effectively identify artefacts in machine-readable text.
4. **Graphing Diverse Textiles Data with IndexGPT:** Workshopping different approaches to text and image parsing, annotation and knowledge extraction from heterogeneously formatted trade directories; unlocking rich and detailed resources that are, as of yet, difficult to make usefully machine-readable.
5. **Neural Radiance Field / Heritage Sites as Lost Mills sub-investigation:** Exploring the use of archival photography and film to construct models of lost build heritage through Neural Radiance Field techniques, geolocating them using maps and spatial data, and aggregating data about historical records of mill company activity from both digital and analogue sources.
6. **Museum online catalogues-as-data:** Surfacing the barriers to direct linkages between online collection catalogues, tracing the histories of catalogue digitisation, the application of multiple, and variously applied, terminologies, and the technical make-up of collections information systems.
7. **The Power of Advertisements:** Experimenting with computer vision tools to identify artefacts in advertisements, to link these with collection records, and to reflect on gendered presentations of appliances and tools.
8. **Industrial occupations:** Developing an ontology of industrial occupations that could act as a backbone for supporting a variety of linkages between people, collections, places and processes. This involves working with datasets of occupation listings, occupations descriptions extracted from trade directories for Bradford Newcastle and taxomised, collections of machines and workers' tools, and open knowledge sources, particularly Wikidata.
9. **Mapping Power Stations:** This examines the take-up of Parsons turbines at power stations across the UK using a visual mapping tool to connect information from sites to spatial data (Historic England), site technical information (Grace's Guide, The Engineer, The Electrician), and data about the establishment of sites and installation of turbines globally (Wikipedia). It is also intended to test the extent to which the course of power lines can be tracked on Ordnance Survey maps, and the ways in which these can be integrated into the visual mapping.

Enabled by our systemic action research approach, the variety of different inquiries is enabling the project to work through micro- and macro- understandings of how researchers might operate within a digitally linked national collection, and how a process of creating a national collection can operate as a social machine. An individual investigation acts as a case study of how a researcher might undertake research using part of the national collection, adopting a variety of different tools and datasets, and rehearsing sophisticated processes, which may become available for general diffusion. Whilst their specific research may be investigating a historical question pertinent to the individual researcher or

project partner, they are also modelling different pipelines for heritage items to be transformed into heritage data, becoming part of a wider, increasingly interlinked, cultural heritage data landscape. We are using mapping exercises and the Investigations Meetings constantly to draw out how the individual investigations intersect and feed into our overall specification of the national collection as a social machine.

Mapping investigations and the pipeline											
Live investigations	Material artefact	Handwritten sources	Printed analogue material	Digitised text material	Image	Moving Image	Audio	Machine readable data	Extractable databases	Annotated sources	Data model sources
🔗 Oral Histories as connective sources			Digitisation and OCR for non-machine readable transcriptions				Speech to text for non-transcribed audio	NER, topic modelling & sentiment analysis	Collection database searches with extracted entities	Annotated transcriptions, connecting objects, places, people and organisations	
🔗 Connecting workers' songs with mining and textile connections: a cross-strand investigation.			Digitisation and OCR for non-machine readable lyric/music sheets			Speech to text for non-transcribed video recordings	Speech to text for non-transcribed audio	Dialect translation, participatory metadata enrichment, NER, topic modelling & sentiment analysis	Collection database searches with extracted entities		
🔗 Neural Radiance Field / Heritage Sites as Lost Mills sub-investigation					NeRF on photos of mills	Segmenting moving image into a series of stills				Geolocated 3D model of mills and spaces	
🔗 The Power of Advertisements					Segmenting and cropping images from digitised magazines			Computer vision, image categorisation	Collection database searches with extracted entities	Annotated images, associated with objects, company records and accounts of gendered advertising	
🔗 Mapping Power Stations				OCR to make PDFs machine readable				NLP, mapping, data cleaning, geospatial plotting		Plotting and connecting collections records within geospatial polygons	
🔗 Deeper catalogue data				OCR to make PDFs machine readable				Ngrams and Surprising phrases analysis			
🔗 Museum online catalogues-as-data				Museum catalogue data exports				Identifying and defining rich & thin records and the (mis)use of taxonomies	Comparing with other museum catalogue exports		
🔗 Industrial occupations				Scraping of Occupations list website				Organising data in a tabulated format and clean	connect with and review in relation to other taxonomical style data		Industrial occupations ontology aiding the description of connective relationships
🔗 Segmenting and abstracting trade directory data											
🔗 No access											

Figure 3: Notion page tabulating how investigations map to different aspects of pipelines between analogue collections items and linkable data.

Decolonising industrial heritage and consciously designing an anti-oppressive national collection

There are multiple approaches to decolonisation and anti-racism currently active in the museums, archives, universities and organisations that make up the landscape of the UK’s national collections. In this strand of work, we are keen to embed them in the design of a national collection. As part of that work, we are exploring the implications of positioning industrial heritage as inextricably linked with colonisation, capitalist expansion and exploitation; that the material remains of the UK’s industrial past may be seen as documents of colonialism. For us, this constitutes a vital step in ensuring datasets created through digital-focused projects on industrial heritage are not decontextualised from the global histories they are a part of.

Congruence Engine is planning a three-step approach to understanding the decolonisation of industrial heritage and, in the process, developing a national collection as social machine that is actively anti-racist and anti-oppressive in how it operates. To do this, we seek to:

1. Connect and map how all our partner organisations are addressing race and decolonisation and to situate that within key sector-wide initiatives. For example, the [Decolonising the Database](#) work undertaken by Collections Trust.

2. Develop a strand of the *Congruence Engine* reading group to read and discuss current relevant work on race, decolonisation and global histories. We understand self-education and reflective work as a key aspect of being able to think about an anti-oppressive national collection for the future.
3. Plan a conference on Decolonising Industrial Heritage for Autumn 2023, drawing in contributions from historians, cultural heritage professionals and anti-racist organisers.

This work will be developing alongside our design specification for a national collection and will be informing both the social and technical aspects of our work.

Technical means for delivery of Historical/Curatorial investigations

In the first phase of the project, a wide variety of readily accessible digital tools was used and critiqued, including as components in pipelines for achieving particular purposes and outputs. These included Omeka-S (chosen as a database solution for hand-stitched linkage but with the potential for semantic modelling against external ontologies and authorities), OpenRefine (for data preparation), SpaCy (for off-the-shelf Named Entity Recognition), Gephi (for network analysis of families and households in a local census record), QGIS and Kepler.gl (for spatial analysis of geocoded Census and Campop data). All these remain in our repertory of tools, though they will increasingly be considered both in relation to their relevance to more complex tasks and larger scale data processing, and as part of an ecology or methods and components within re-configurable pipelines.

Use of Omeka-S is currently paused but it is likely to be resumed in relation to the consideration of other database technologies that offer either semantic or pseudo-semantic capabilities: Neo4j, with its inbuilt graph visualisation feature, briefly tested alongside Omeka-S and now being further tested in relation to one larger dataset, initially, and then potentially as a point of aggregation, as well as a sandbox for experimentation with AI knowledge graph generation. Future planned tested of databases: Arches, as a database and data management system that is well-supported by various prominent cultural heritage organisations, including some partners, for particular applications, and includes basic inbuilt geospatial (Mapbox-based) and graph (Cytoscape-derived) visualisation; GraphDB by Ontotext, with its associated incarnation of OpenRefine (OntoRefine), for the generation of directly ingestible RDF triples; and the relatively untested but promising TerminusDB, which may offer advantages for certain user-groups.

Having identified a particular challenge around the alignment of database fields from diverse sources for linkage and ingestion, we have also initiated conversations with Seattle-based Osmos about their promising proprietary software.

Upstream, a variety of methods for image parsing and segmentation were tested as a first step towards data extraction from the large collection of historic Trade Directories held by the University of Leicester, during and around a collaborative hackathon with the Turing Institute, including additional experiments with scripted approaches to working with image-segmented semi-tabulated text. Alongside this, tests by core Congruence Engine researchers using the most recent version of Abbyfinereader (off-the-shelf image segmentation and OCR) on specific Newcastle and Bradford trade directories have produced good results that allow the confident inclusion of this material in exhibit planning, mapped and analysed for change over time. The effectiveness of Abbyfinereader for this purpose, superseding the use of PyTesseract scripting for OCR, has prompted its wider adoption within the project for the preparation of

larger corpora of folk songs, initially, mentioned below. In a simpler experiment with image recognition, the VIS and VIC tools created by the Oxford Virtual Geometry Group are being applied to hand-segmented images from printed magazines to identify domestic appliances; other methods, including multi-modal image parsing, may subsequently be tested to refine or more fully automate the process, and perhaps for application to the analysis of shots from moving image (BFI) sources.

Current work with the University of Leicester has involved the preparation of textual corpora derived from audio sources, using the Whisper speech-to-text model (OpenAI), the use of the Bertopic transformer-based modelling technique (using models based on FlairNLP, developed and published by Prof Alan Akbik at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, and RoBERTa-Twitter, developed and published by the Research Group in Natural Language Processing at Cardiff University) to generate clustering in high-dimensional space, and UMAP dimensionality reduction techniques applied to visualise these topics in two-dimensional space for analysis, with further analysis conducted using Tableau tools.

Following the restrictions imposed on ChatGPT by regulators in Italy over privacy concerns (30/3/2023), and on the personal preference of the Leicester researcher, the use of these more advanced methods has been temporarily suspended, and we will be pursuing this as an opportunity to actively examine the practical and ethical considerations arising, possibly including with specialist advice.

Similar methods (eg Bertopic/RoBERTa) are expected to be used and tested in the collaboration with the Sussex Text Analysis Group Lab, assuming no wider regulatory restrictions before that work begins, with a distinctive application to creating candidate alignment between content of collections metadata fields, for purposes of linkage/integration. Additionally, initial collaborative work with MadLab has begun testing the capabilities of ChatGPT (OpenAI) for generating knowledge graphs from tabulated data and text corpora, including the construction of prompts and tuning with domain-specific datasets. In light of the highly promising potential of these and similar technologies as key components of a National Collection social machine, and with a mid-term anticipatory view to risk management and mitigation during the construction of a National Collection, there is a clear need to develop a good understanding of this fast-developing field and recommendations, insofar as they are possible.

Other work undertaken since December to explore digital methods has built on Phase 1 use of bespoke code has been applied to (a) extract n-grams (uni-, tri-, bi-) for initial probe of free text content (eg collections data field) and to start building vocabularies; (b) reconstruct genealogies from complex Census household-relation descriptions; (c) scrape website of hierarchical occupations descriptions into cleaned and tabulated form. The first-phase of development of an 'Occupations' ontology and a series of associated entity-specific (place, activity, object, material, etc) data resources has formed a distinct area of proof-of-concept activity over the last nine months, and more recently that has been extended to include the local trade directories for two cities, from which tests have been carried out to extract and model occupations for inclusion in the exhibit plans. Related to this, and otherwise, we are starting to test the training of SpaCy for domain-specific named entity recognition, while also considering the possible solutions available for expert annotation of text to generate machine-readable XML (Prodigy, Recogito, even Word, etc) along with the institutional issues around hosting of tools/platforms for collaborative work.

This 'Occupations' work intersects with several other investigations, including the aggregation of data related to the 'Lost Mills' of Bradford, which involves a practical investigation of how to integrate controlled vocabularies and thesauri, and polygonised data requests, as required by Historic England's suite of diverse databases. Associated with this, and testing the challenges of bringing together photographs of specific interior locations from diverse sources, a 'Reanimating Lost Mills' sub-project will be experimenting with Neural Radiance Imaging computer vision methods, as a means to generate 3D scenes that may serve both as a basis for immersive encounters with the past and as interfaces that inherently represent the partiality of the historical (visual) record.

Research Results

In our previous report we drew attention to four interlinked areas: ‘Cross-collections research is, for many, a novel proposition’; ‘Linking collections for new kinds of historical research’ (pointing to intermedial forms of history); ‘Affordances of different kinds of heritage in creating a national collection’ (alluding to the necessity of using data within national collection items to create linking ontologies) and ‘Appreciating multi/interdisciplinary cultural differences’. In line with the emergent approach that our systemic action research methodology employs, we gave space for these early research findings to develop, and used a variety of reflection techniques to begin crystalizing what they might mean for the work of Congruence Engine in progress. In the period since the last report, our ongoing experimentation around the ‘affordances of different kinds of heritage in creating a national collection’ and ‘appreciating multi/interdisciplinary cultural differences’ has helped us to cohere our thinking around the main thrust of the project’s leading concept, the national collection as a social machine. A recent project workshop on creating the national collection via social machines (27-28 March 2023) has helped catalyse those early insights towards the beginnings of the design specification to be delivered in the next year. This section of the report surfaces the aspects of a national collection as social machine that are proving particularly resonant with the project, and that are being developed further through existing and newly forming lines of investigation.

National Collection as Social Machine

The first report indicated our emerging focus. We noted the ‘potential of linking collections for new kinds of historical and curatorial practice, both by people who are paid to do history, and those who do it for fun’, but also the cultural and professional differences between the different communities of practitioners who work in and with cultural heritage and collections. We also evoked our tentative descriptions of this as ‘to national collection’ as a verb, denoting the sense that the national collection should not be seen as a noun – something that already exists awaiting linkage – but something that is created by means of co-production using digital techniques. (Compare Christopher Small’s exploration of ‘Musicking’ (1998).)

‘Social machine’ had been a term in our conversation since our kick-off conference; it featured in the project ‘North Star’, our co-developed statement of purpose, created in the conference’s final session (figure 4). It appeared again during a conversation about the multiplicity of ways of interacting with a national collection at a reflection workshop, towards the end of the first nine months of investigations.

Figure 4: Post-It notes from facilitated session on the project ‘North Star’, Bradford, February 2022.

Since then, we have been specifying further what it might mean to ‘verb’ the national collection and how that might relate to the concept of a social machine. In recent months, we have been particularly interested in how we might draw on the characteristics and metaphor of ‘social machine’ to give shape and communicative power to our work.

The idea of ‘social machine’ is often traced to Tim Berners-Lee with Mark Fischett in their 1999 ‘Weaving the Web’. They suggested:

Real life is and must be full of all kinds of social constraint – the very processes from which society arises. Computers can help if we use them to create abstract social machines on the Web; processes in which people do the creative work and the machine does the administration. [...] The stage is set for an evolutionary growth of new social engines. The ability to create new social process would be given to the world at large, and development would be rapid. (pp. 172-5)

Since then, it has been elaborated in various contexts not least by [a conference convened by Wikipedia](#) in 2014 and by a major EPSRC funded project called [SOCIAM](#), which has led to a major edited collection *The Theory and Practice of Social Machines* (Shadbolt, O’Hara, De Roure and Hall 2019). We draw inspiration from this work, but do not subscribe to all of its aspects. The immediate relevance to our project is captured by our lead for Digital History Alex Butterworth in his ‘manifesto’ contribution to the *Science Museum Group Journal Congruence Engine* special issue (2022; all further quotations in this section come from this source). Butterworth evokes Congruence Engine as ‘a “social machine” that coordinates and harmonises a range of digital technologies, and human curiosity and capabilities, to generate new constellations of collective knowledge’.

Reflecting and elaborating the characteristics of social machine also described by Shadbolt, O’Hara, De Roure and Hall, Butterworth identified a number of ways in which Congruence Engine might be operating as a social machine. Since then, we have been following a number of lines of inquiry, pursuing how Congruence Engine can model the following aspects of a national collection as social machine:

- How a national collection needs to be made through a diverse range of generative and collaborative forms of contribution.
- How the organisation of a national collection needs to be both federated and emergent in relation to how it is generated, sustained and maintained.
- How the human and the digital (or social and machine) aspects of a national collection need to be in constant iterative dialogue.

Made through Contribution

The national collection is verbed – an active ongoing doing – as it is constantly produced through the links researchers themselves make using digital means. The orientation of a national collection as social machine is provisional and uncertain, recognizing both that is a function of machine techniques (such as ‘candidate recognition’) and human interpretation – an ongoing ‘invitation to improvement’.

Our focus now, as we explain above under ‘Research Approach’, is to materialise this through a pipeline that starts out with collections items, and takes them from analogue to machine-readable form, and then on to annotated data sets and beyond – to open and linkable data models and ‘generously’ explorable data. At each point of the pipeline, a combination of human and technical processes is

necessary. We have begun to identify the points within the workflows where participatory activities are necessary, for example: in checking OCR results, or in the use of domain expertise to annotate images for computer vision model training, or in the confirmation and organisation of relevant controlled vocabularies.

Federated and Emergent Legitimacy

The question of structure and governance is clearly central to our proposition about how a digitally mediated national collection can be created. A social machine is forged in a distributed structure ‘allowing ownership of digitised knowledge to be kept local, control to be federated, expertise to be valorised, and contribution to be micro-accredited’. The term ‘national collection’ risks seeming top-down and dominated by national GLAM organisations, not to mention chauvinistic connotations of patriotism. The benefit of our approach, by contrast, is that it enables the (verbed) national collection to draw ‘its propulsive energy from a wide community that represents the diversity of the twenty-first century nation, at all levels of the engine’s design and operation, and which confers its legitimacy and ensures its sustainability’. This ongoing negotiation of the ‘national’, and desire to identify ways of recognising the significance of heritage across different scales, is a consideration across multiple TaNC Foundation and Discovery projects (Paltrinieri, 2023). The vision is ultimately to create ‘a new and radical vision of knowledge production as a site of active citizenship, in which cultural heritage communities-of-interest are in a continual and fluid process of coalescence to the mutual benefit of those involved’.

In practical terms, we will investigate the governance issues through targeted interviews with different potential participants in the creation of a national collection. That, in turn, will inform further experimental action to enact and refine how a federated approach might work. This will be investigated in step with our ongoing work on decolonisation so as to ensure that the design of a national collection as social machine operates as an anti-racist, anti-colonial and anti-oppressive enterprise.

Human and Technology in Endless Loops

In 1999, Berners-Lee and Fischett envisioned a clear division between creative and non-creative work that, in our usage of the social machine metaphor, we would need to challenge. But it is key to our design intentions constantly to make creative use of the different affordances of scaled-up and scaled-out processing capabilities, both machine and human. That ‘constitutes a mechanism for negotiation between human and computationally legible information, which must recognise and mediate twin ideals: of precision and standardisation; and expressive nuance, idiosyncrasy and fluidity’. An affordance of human-technological collaboration is to be ‘conscientiously calibrated to mitigate bias, as a hybrid social machine, and continuously retuned to capture (and discover) previously overlooked or excluded areas of knowledge that challenge, refine, expand and reshape national stories’.

We have developed from the ‘hand-stitched’ investigations of our first year to larger and more complex inquiries that actively experiment with the different interfaces between human and the digital (the social and the machine). These investigations ‘manage knowledge whose operation crosses multiple spatial and temporal scales and levels of detail. Ease of movement between these states is a key principle for the exploratory but contextualized representation of that knowledge’.

Our new approach to the multiple investigations has been to design them with active consideration of three discrete but interconnected aspects so that we can maximise the clarity of our 'design specification' for a national collection conceived as a social machine:

- What to do: the potential digital insights – what tools, techniques and processes might be used or developed?
- Which people: who needs to be involved, what requirements are there on their time, and how can we take an ethical approach to valuing and crediting input across a range of different material realities?
- To what end: the potential historical insights – how, in making the connections between different collections using digital techniques and people's knowledge, can we generate new insights about our industrial heritage and beyond?

To take one example: in our investigation that looks into broadside ballads and work-related folk songs, there is an iterative interplay between the digital techniques (speech to text and entity extraction) and the human and social (contributions of expertise from industrial folk historians and performers). The investigation is indicating how sound heritage can act as a connective source in telling better informed histories of working-class people's lives and experiences in industrial societies. This investigation is also testing an approach to enable a broad range of expertise to be accommodated within a contributory model of participation in a national collection as social machine.

Project Outputs

The Project Blog has so far featured:

- We are *Congruence Engine*: Metaphors and Project Conduct (22 Feb 2022)
- Methods: Seeking congruence and enabling divergence (14 March 2022)
- The *Congruence Engine* opening conference – enacting the principles of systemic action research (24 March 2022)
- *Congruence Engine* North Star (24 March 2022)
- Energising materials, connecting stories – local, national and international (25 May 2022)
- What can Omeka do for your digital journey? Reflections from the first *Congruence Engine* Pilot Study (1 Jul 2022)
- Co-producing research inquiries for the textiles strand (2 Aug 2022)
- Reflecting on the Textiles Pilot (22 Aug 2022)
- Trying out Gale Digital Scholar Lab (18 Oct 2022)
- Giving voice to hidden collections: Insights from the oral history investigation (27 Oct 2022)
- Occupations, Machines, People: The connective tissue that helps us connect collections (11 Jan 2023)
- Directory Enquiries: Machine learning to unlock radical historical context, part one (6 Feb 2023)

Reports

Shoaib Sufi, Emily Bell, & Anna-Maria Sichani. (2023). Report on the AHRC Digital/ Software Requirements Survey 2021: Where is Investment Needed? (1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686348>

Magazine Publications

Rees, Arran. opinion piece, *Museums Journal* (Museum Association Magazine), Jan/Feb 2022, pp 12., <https://www.museumsassociation.org/museums-journal/opinion/2022/01/digital-the-potential-of-ai/>

Boon, Tim. “The Congruence Engine.” *Viewpoint* (BSHS Magazine), no. 126, Feb. 2022, pp. 8–9. <https://www.bsbs.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/No-126-Feb-2022-for-web.pdf>

Congruence Engine special issue of the Science Museum Group Journal

A double-sized special issue of the *Science Museum Group Journal* showcasing the *Congruence Engine* project was published in early 2023. This edition contains 18 papers featuring experimental and new forms of writing that include scene-setting pieces, collaborative authorship, and single-author essays with writers contributing their individual skill and perspective, and other pieces which explore what it means to come together within the project. [Autumn 2023 - Science Museum Group Journal](#)

The published issue contains the following articles:

Author	Article	Article type/subject/origin
Introduction/Editorial		
Tim Boon	Origins and Ambitions of the Congruence Engine Project	Single author article
Helen Graham, Arran Rees	Congruence Engine in action	Editorial
Alex Butterworth	The Congruence Engine Manifesto	Single author article
Research papers		
Will Ashworth	History of textiles and the Congruence Engine	Single author article
Paul Craddock	Connecting with industrial heritage and collections using video production methods	Short video and film essay
Tim Smith	Textiles in the modern age	Photo essay
John Stack, Jamie Unwin	The potential and pitfalls of machine learning in the Congruence Engine context	Two-author article
Graeme Gooday, Kylea Little, Bernard Musesengwe, Cameron Tailford	Energising connections in museum collections	Multi-author article
Asa Calow	The future: reflections on emerging machine learning methods for digital heritage	Single author article
Discussion papers/Conversations		
Arran Rees, Anna-Maria Sichani and Stefania Zardini Lacedelli	Surfacing multiple perspectives on keywords for the Congruence Engine; embracing multiplicity, interdisciplinarity, and mutual learning	Conversation
Kylea Little, Ellie Swinbank, Felicity McWilliams	'South Kensington is practically as far away as Munich': the making of Industrial Collections in Edinburgh, Newcastle and Birmingham	Discussion paper
Ben Rusell and Wayne Cocroft	Connecting places and collections	Two-author hybrid: discussion / photo essay
Jon Agar	History of communications and the Congruence Engine: early thoughts and possibilities	Single author article
Daniel C S Wilson	Working at scale: what do computational methods mean for research using cases, models and collections?	Single author article

Simon Popple and Stefania Zardini Lacedelli, Arran J Rees, Stuart Prior, and Maggie Smith	Collaborative conversation as a method for exploring multiple perspectives on 'community' and forms of knowledge in the Congruence Engine	Conversation piece
Jane Winters and Anna-Maria Sichani	The role of digital humanities in an interdisciplinary research project	Two-author article
Review		
Lauren Ryall-White	Living with Machines	
Obituary		
Tim Boon and Graeme Gooday	Cameron James Tailford (Research Fellow), 10 October 1991 – 3 August 2022	

Cross-project Collaboration

Cross-project collaboration is beginning to emerge as the Discovery Projects mature and begin to make findings within their respective special concerns. We foresee two likely contributions Congruence Engine can make:

- As our own experiments with database technologies and their interoperability and potential ecologies develop, we will be seeking to convene a cross-TaNC working group to share knowledge and insights. Our emerging and experimental strategy of developing data resources - vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, gazetteers and the ontologies to relate them around event structures - which are both formalised and flexible enough to accommodate diverse expression (perhaps even divergent option), will be tested on our own domain-defined range of data sources. To establish proof-of-concept for the validity of this in a broader context, however, we aim to work with our collaborating (unfunded partner) project, Tools of Knowledge, to test the application of its Scientific Apparatus Ontology to create candidates for linkage in three TaNC Discovery project datasets - Congruence Engine (Science Museum/National Museums Scotland), Sloane Lab and Unpathe'd Waters - and in consultation with a possible similar initiative between Tools of Knowledge and the Museum Data Service.
- The proposed workshop on decolonising industrial heritage (see 8.3.3).

Sustainability and Infrastructure

The project continues to develop and refine its infrastructure for communicating within the team as well as for storing, documenting, sharing and preserving data, code and other outputs.

A key development has been the introduction of [Notion](#) as a platform for supporting collaborative documentation and knowledge exchange across the project, alongside the existing use of BaseCamp for wider project communication. All members of the team can find information about: project meetings; ongoing research investigations; developing project pipelines; events and publications; project partners; and the *Congruence Engine* approach to ethics.

Two sections within the Notion wiki contain detailed information about data and datasets and the activity of core team members, including investigators and research fellows. The pages on 'data documentation' include a database with information about all datasets identified, requested and collected; guidance on data datasets documentation, file-naming conventions etc. Nine members of the team with full editing rights (guest editors can be added to particular pages at no cost) have also been adding weekly reflective notes, which describe what they have been working on as well as any thoughts and ideas that have been sparked by collaboration. Supplemented by general team updates and newsletters, this feature has been enormously beneficial in creating a sense of shared ownership across the project.

Dataset	Description	CE Theme	Assigned to	Status	Status date	CE Investigati...	Priority
Factory returns	Parliamentary Papers dating from 1835 and 1836	Textiles Energy	Daniel Belteki	No action			
South West Coalfield Collection	Oral history recordings relating to mining in Wales	Energy	Daniel Belteki	In dialogue	12/12/2022		
Films related to textiles from the BFI	JSON file of BFI holdings related to textiles.	Textiles	Stefania	Collected	06/01/2023	Re-animating Lo	
Films/Audio-Visual materials related to coal minin	JSON export of records from the BFI relating to cc	Energy	Daniel Belteki	Collected	06/12/2022		
Mining / Energy Collections Catalogue (Birmi	CSV catalogue of mining and steam related object	Energy	Daniel Belteki	Collected	06/12/2022		
Mining Collections Catalogue (NCMM)	CSV catalogue of the National Coal Mining Museu	Energy	Daniel Belteki	Collected	06/12/2022		
Photos of Power Stations	Photos from the various archival collections at His	Energy	Daniel Belteki	In dialogue	06/12/2022		
Entries related to Saltaire and Lister Mill	Subset from the Warden files & aerial photograph	Textiles	Stefania	Collected	06/01/2023	Re-animating Lo	
Lost Mills photographs (UK)	Images of Mills that no longer exists - across the l	Textiles Energy	Alex Butterwort			Re-animating Lo	
Saltaire Collection	CSV catalogue of the Saltaire collection	Textiles	Stefania	Collected	06/01/2023		
Saltaire Collection Oral Histories	Oral history collection of people living and workin	Textiles	Stefania	Collected	06/01/2023		
Bradford Heritage Recording Unit	Oral history collection of Bradford Museum and G.	Textiles	Stefania	In dialogue			
Textile Voices	The digitized version of the 'Textile Voices' public	Textiles	Stefania	Collected	06/01/2023		

Figure 5: 'Datasets' database in Notion

For data ingestion and short-term storage, a light version of Box has been employed, to address the immediate imperative of gathering data for inspection and assessment, as a first step towards the aggregation of partners' datasets (master files), with parallel attention to the size of the data, the diversity of file formats and the different licensing frameworks that apply. Additional or alternative requirements for data storage and management will be analysed and solutions tested, as they arise. A [project-owned GitHub repository](#) is also maintained so that working datasets and code can be shared and developed among team members as part of ongoing investigations. A dedicated data management

task has been assigned to the Digital Humanities Research Fellow to ensure smooth and efficient data ingestion and sustainability throughout the project. A responsible open access strategy informs the data management, processing and infrastructure choices throughout the project.

Training, and in particular the development of digital skills among team members and project partners, is an important aspect of how the project views sustainability. A three-tier training programme has been adopted, which balances the acquisition of generic core skills with more specific needs arising directly from the practical experience of the project. Fortnightly drop-in sessions allow researchers to talk through their data and research questions on an informal basis with data scientists (and vice versa). These sessions also help to surface immediate training needs that arise from investigations, which can be followed up relatively rapidly with bespoke provision on an individual or small-group basis. Finally, a [more structured general training programme](#) introduces key digital tools and concepts, for example the use of GitHub or the broad concepts of linked open data and machine learning for cultural heritage.

Interim Recommendations

Approach

The project recommends that the creation of the national collection be undertaken through linkage between existing and specially-created 'connective tissue' data rather than by systematised aggregation of identically formatted data.

Audiences for digital collections

Whilst we want to ensure a national collection has broad appeal, we should not fall into the trap of thinking the national collection needs to be everything to everyone. Creation and use of a national collection must take account of participants' motivations, enabling them to become involved in ways that feel useful to them.

Data and digital assets

Accessing data is a more complex process than it might initially seem; the heritage sector uses differing standards and often uses dated relational databases from which export requires human resource. The project recommends further investment in APIs for the sector rather than relying on data exports and data and digital asset transfers.

Tools and standards

The speed at which digital tools and techniques are developing makes it difficult to recommend investing in fixed systems, tools and machine learning techniques. Instead, Congruence Engine recommends development of a suite (or registry) of tools and services that can be maintained and updated, allowing researchers and national collection users to choose those most appropriate for them, depending on their needs and the datasets in question.

Congruence Engine recommends that no attempt is made to create a new overarching data standard, but instead, a series of standard data mappings that allow collections of different types (archive, museums, libraries, Wikidata, personal collections or community archives) to be linked.

Pipelines

A national collection should offer multiple flexible pipeline processes to enable people to contribute, analyse and connect collections depending on their specific requirements.

It is important to consider the usage of technical language, such as 'pipelines', in describing the findings of the towards a national collection project.

Digitisation and digitalisation

Congruence Engine recommends rethinking digitisation processes that only result in a digital image or a flat digital file. The Congruence Engine pipeline is interested in digitisation processes that make analogue material machine readable.

Congruence Engine recommends TaNC adopt a broad definition of 'the national collection' to incorporate datasets including, for example, the census, or data from within archives rendered machine-readable, that through their affordances as 'connective tissue' may enable the linkage of conventional GLAM collection items such as objects or pictures.

People and skills

Congruence Engine recommends clear specifications for both social and technical infrastructural resource. Technology alone cannot create a sustainable and generative national collection.

Alongside any resource for technical infrastructure, resource for training and long-term skills development is needed. Currently there exists no career path for digital heritage specialists, and existing historical and curatorial practitioners are not equipped to undertake the more digital forms of practice that we can expect to become normal in the near future.

There are important questions to be addressed relating to the siloeing of different kinds of expertise – digital, historical and curatorial – often reinforced by distinct language and working cultures. We recommend investment in career paths for individuals to gain hybrid skills to enable the linked national collection within the coming age of more digital curatorship and scholarship.

Diversity and Governance

A national collection as social machine will need a distributed and federated governance structure, one that enables local decision-making and contribution and does not require central control. A major focus of our next phase of work will be to understand what this might mean and how it might be designed.

Industrial heritage is a record of British colonial expansion and capitalist extraction. To see the national collection as a social machine offers a means of understanding how better to approach this subject, by activating different collections, knowledge and positions.

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